

Synthesis of 2-Phenylimino-3-aryl/*H*-4-*S*-benzyl-6-tetra-*O*-acetyl-*D*-glucopyranosylimino-2,3-dihydro-1,3,5-thiadiazines

B. N. BERAD, S. P. DESHMUKH and M. G. PARANJPE*

Department of Chemistry, Nagpur University, Nagpur-440 010

Manuscript received 18 January 1984, accepted 30 May 1984

2-Phenylimino-3-aryl/*H*-4-*S*-benzyl-6-tetra-*O*-acetyl-*D*-glucopyranosylimino-2, 3-dihydro-1,3,5-thiadiazine hydrochlorides (IIIa-IIIf) have been synthesized directly by the interaction of phenyl isocyanodichloride (I) and 1-aryl/*H*-5-tetra-*O*-acetyl-*D*-glucopyranosyl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (IIa-III). Their structures have been supported on the basis of usual chemical transformations and ir spectral data. These could not be isomerised into corresponding 1,3,5-triazines.

RECENTLY, we have prepared 1-aryl/*H*-5-tetra-*O*-acetyl-*D*-glucopyranosyl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (II) by the interaction of 1-aryl/*H*-*S*-benzylisothiocarbamide and tetra-*O*-acetyl-*D*-glucopyranosylisothiocyanate¹. In view of our interest in *N*-glucosylated compounds, we now report the synthesis of 2-phenylimino-3-aryl/*H*-4-*S*-benzyl-6-tetra-*O*-acetyl-*D*-glucopyranosylimino-2,3-dihydro-1,3,5-thiadiazines.

The reaction of phenylisocyanodichloride² (I) and 1-phenyl-5-tetra-*O*-acetyl-*D*-glucopyranosyl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (IIa) in boiling benzene medium afforded a clear yellow solution. On distilling out benzene a syrupy mass was left. This on repeated triturations with petroleum ether gave a pale yellow solid, m.p. 110° (d). It was found unstable and on standing gradually decomposed into a sticky material. The product was found desulphurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution. The product was acidic to litmus and gave effervescence with aqueous

sodium bicarbonate solution. It gave a picrate m.p. 172°. The product has $[\alpha]_D^{25} -26.99^\circ$ (c 0.4 in CHCl₃); ν_{max} 1750, (C=O), 685 (C-S), 1595 (S-C=N), and 1580 cm⁻¹ (N-C=N) bands^{3,4}. Bands due to the isotriazine ring structure at 1550 and 750 cm⁻¹ were missing. Therefore, the product has been assigned the structure 2-phenylimino-3-phenyl-4-*S*-benzyl-6-tetra-*O*-acetyl-*D*-glucopyranosylimino-2,3-dihydro-1,3,5-thiadiazine hydrochloride (IIIa).

The reaction of phenylisocyanodichloride has been extended to other 1-aryl/*H*-5-tetra-*O*-acetyl-*D*-glucopyranosyl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets to obtain IIIb to IIIf (Table 1).

Isomerisation of these 1,3,5-thiadiazines (III) have been tried in several ways but without success. Also, these could not be deacetylated into the corresponding *D*-glucopyranosyl forms, when tried with methanolic ammonia.

TABLE 1—2-PHENYLIMINO-3-ARYL/*H*-4-*S*-BENZYL-6-TETRA-*O*-ACETYL-*D*-GLUCOPYRANOSYLIMINO-2,3-DIHYDRO-1,3,5-THIADIAZINE (HYDROCHLORIDE) (II)

1-Aryl/*H*-5-tetra-*O*-acetyl-*D*-glucopyranosyl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets used : 0.01 *M*.
N-Phenylisocyanodichloride used : 1.8 g

Sl. no.	Isodithiobiuret used (g)	1,3,5-Thiadiazine hydrochloride (III), yield (g)	Yield %	M.p. °C(d)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		Eq. wt. Found/ (Calcd.)	$[\alpha]_D^{25}$ in CHCl ₃ , deg	Picrate M.p. °C	N% Found/ (Calcd.)
1.	1-Phenyl (6.3)	-3-phenyl . . (6.5), IIIa	80	110	7.28 (7.28)	8.32 (8.23)	761.4 (768.5)	-26.99 (c 0.40)	172	9.83 (10.19)
2.	1- <i>o</i> -Tolyl (6.5)	-3- <i>o</i> -tolyl . . (5.8), IIIb	71	78	6.59 (7.15)	7.77 (8.17)	772.8 (782.5)	-31.90 (c 0.40)	108	9.52 (10.05)
3.	1- <i>p</i> -tolyl (6.5)	-3- <i>p</i> -tolyl . . (6.0), IIIc	73	105	6.89 (7.15)	8.30 (8.17)	770.2 (782.5)	+18.40 (c 0.40)	120	9.67 (10.05)
4.	1- <i>o</i> -Cl-phenyl (6.6)	-3- <i>o</i> -Cl-phenyl . . (5.5), IIId	65	115	6.83 (6.97)	8.03 (7.97)	790.2 (803.0)	-28.31 (c 0.40)	95d	9.63 (9.84)
5.	1- <i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl (6.6)	-3- <i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl . . (5.8), IIIe	69	82	6.64 (6.97)	7.00 (7.97)	794.0 (803.0)	+56.25 (c 0.40)	151d	9.58 (9.84)
6.	1-Hydrogen (5.5)	-3-hydrogen . . (5.5), IIIf	87	132	7.62 (8.08)	9.31 (9.24)	680.0 (692.5)	-22.09 (c 0.40)	Not isolated	

The compounds gave satisfactory C and H analyses.

Where, R = phenyl, o-tolyl, p-tolyl, o-Cl-phenyl, p-Cl-phenyl, hydrogen.
 TAG = Tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl,
 Bz = Benzyl, G = D-glucopyranosyl.

Experimental

2-Phenylimino-3-aryl-1,3,5-thiadiazine hydrochloride (III): Details of a typical experiment (where aryl=phenyl) are as follows.

To a suspension of 1-phenyl-5-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl-2-S-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (0.01 M, 6.3 g) in benzene (50 ml) was added phenylisocyanodichloride (0.01 M, 1.8 g) and the mixture refluxed for 4 h. The evolution of hydrogen chloride was noticed. Benzene was distilled off and a syrupy mass was left. The mass on repeated trituration with petroleum ether gave a pale yellow solid (6.5 g). The product was purified by precipitating it from its benzene solution with petroleum ether. m.p. 110°(d) (Found: C, 49.20; H, 4.62; N, 7.28; S, 8.32; Eq. wt., 761.4. C₃₈H₃₈O₉N₄S₂. HCl requires C, 49.22; H, 4.87; N, 7.28; S, 8.23%; Eq. wt., 768.5). Its ethanolic solution on reaction with picric acid afforded a picrate crystal-

lised from ethanol-water, m.p. 172° (Found: N, 9.83. C₄₂H₄₀O₁₀N₇S₂ requires N, 10.19%).

Acknowledgement

Two of the authors (S.P.D and B.N.B.) are grateful to U.G.C. and C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the award of Junior Research Fellowships, and to Prof. K. N. Munshi for facilities.

References

1. S. P. DESHMUKH, B. N. BERAD and M. G. PARANJPE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, communicated.
2. G. M. DYSON and T. HARRINGTON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 191.
3. N. B. COLTHUP, C. H. DALY and S. E. WIBERLEY, "Introduction to Infrared and Raman Spectroscopy", Academic Press, New York, 1963, p. 215.
4. R. M. SILVERSTEIN and G. C. BASSLER, "Spectrometric Identification of Organic Compounds", John Wiley, New York, 1963.